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Effect of Active Atmosphere Packaging using Natural Fungicide on Quality Characteristics and Shelf Life of Kinnow Fruit

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to evaluate the influence of active packaging parameters i.e., dose of scavenger (3-5 g), fungicide concentration (5-7%), and polythene thickness (100-200 gauge) on the postharvest quality and shelf life of *Citrus reticulata* (kinnow) under cold storage. Response Surface Methodology (RSM) with Box Behnken Design (BBD) was employed to model and optimize the effects on key quality attributes, including O₂ and CO₂ gas concentration, physiological loss in weight, firmness, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, color difference, microbial load, and shelf life. Results indicated that higher doses of scavenger, increased fungicide concentration, and thicker films significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced O₂ and CO₂ levels, delayed ripening, retained firmness and nutritional quality, and minimized microbial growth, ultimately extending shelf life up to 65 days. The mathematical model suggested a high coefficient of determination with optimum conditions as 5 g dose of scavenger, 6.83% fungicide concentration and 192.12 gauge polythene thickness. A non-significant ($p < 0.05$) difference was observed in the actual and predicted values of dependent variables. The findings suggest that active packaging incorporating optimized combinations of scavengers, natural fungicides, and polymer thickness can effectively preserve the quality of kinnow during cold storage. This approach offers a promising, low-residue alternative to conventional chemical treatments for enhancing citrus shelf life in postharvest handling systems.

Keywords: Active packaging; Coating; Fungicide; Kinnow; LDPE; Scavenger; Shelf life

Introduction

'Kinnow' (*Citrus deliciosa* × *Citrus nobilis*) is the foremost citrus fruit of Punjab, and more than half of the total area covered with fruit is occupied by only this cultivar. In Punjab, January and February are the best times for its harvesting, but its demand remains constant throughout the year. At room temperature, it can be stored only for 7-8 days, so unable to fulfil its long-term demand.

Moreover, the lack of processing facilities and cold chain infrastructure during peak harvest season forces farmers to sell their produce at minimal prices in local markets (Randhawa et al., 2009). Being high in moisture, soft, and debilitating nature, the fruits undergo a significant postharvest loss, including microbial spoilage, weight loss, physiological damage, physical damage, and reduced

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nutritional quality (Bhan et al., 2022). The reason behind its short shelf life is the evaporation of moisture at a higher rate when stored without cuticles (Dhall, 2013). Certainly, there is an urgent need to look for appropriate approaches that could maintain the quality of food for the long term and reduce postharvest losses.

During or after the harvesting of fruits, the balance of gases between oxygen consumption and carbon dioxide production has changed (Dhall, 2013). Several techniques, such as active packaging, surface coating, etc., are available to maintain the after-harvest life in fruits (Adhikary et al., 2022). Nowadays, consumers are aware of the cons of commonly used sanitizing techniques and are looking for safe, fresh, healthy, and easy-to-prepare food with high quality retention. To satisfy the requirements of consumers, active packaging (use of scavengers or certain agents) is used, which is a very innovative development in the area of packaging, based on deliberate interactions with the food itself or its environment (Ramos et al., 2013). Components included in active packaging are capable of scavenging O₂, CO₂, moisture, and ethylene and also remove undesirable flavours (De Kruijff et al., 2002). Various researchers have explored the use of scavengers such as Iron-based O₂ scavenger in oranges (Yadav and Ray, 2010), "Bartlett" pears (Kumar and Thakur, 2020), ethylene adsorber in Broccoli (Esturk et al., 2013), and economical adsorbents in sewage water treatment (Jha et al., 2024) etc. In another study on strawberries, O₂ and CO₂ scavengers were simultaneously used, which extended the shelf life up to 4 weeks at 4°C (Aday et al., 2011).

Apart from this, it is worth mentioning that, during washing/precleaning, the natural wax coating on fruit skin is removed, and it is essential to replace it with different synthetic and natural coating materials (Ali et al., 2015). Coatings on fresh produce can reduce quantity and quality losses by controlling and changing their inside atmosphere. Coatings can also reduce the migration of solute and moisture, rates of oxidative reactions, aerobic metabolism, and gas exchange, thereby extending the shelf life. Moreover, it is capable of carrying out some active ingredients like antimicrobials and anti-browning agents that can further enhance the shelf life of food and also reduce the chance of pathogen growth on its surface (Dhall, 2013). After harvesting, deterioration of produce due to fungus can be controlled by synthetic or chemical coatings. However, there are some hurdles in the use of chemical coatings, i.e., concerns of the public regarding their leftovers in produce and an increase in the resistance of pathogens. The use of coatings that are plant-based (natural) and biodegradable might be a good alternative to chemical coatings, which can also fulfil the requirements of consumers for healthy and natural foods (Mahajan et al., 2018).

Taking into consideration the aforesaid properties, neem leaf powder was chosen to evaluate its efficacy for the extension of Kinnow shelf life. Azadirachtin is an active substance present in neem, which is known for its insecticidal, growth-regulating, nematocidal, and fungicidal properties (Malik et al., 2016). In recent studies, neem oil on kinnow fruit, followed by HDPE packaging, has been explored (Randhawa et al., 2009). In another study, Gupta and Jain (2014) used neem leaf extract as a coating on Mango fruits cv. Dashehri.

However, to the best of our knowledge, the combined effect of various scavengers and neem leaf powder coating on postharvest quality attributes of kinnow fruit has not yet been studied. Therefore, the present study was designed to optimize the process parameters, namely the dose of scavenger, fungicide concentration, and polythene thickness and to evaluate their effect on preserving the kinnow quality and enhancing its shelf life.

Materials and Methods

Freshly harvested uniform-sized mature kinnow fruits were procured from the local market, Ludhiana.

Experimental procedure

Preparation of Neem leaf powder (Natural Fungicide)

The neem leaves were collected and washed with tap water to remove adhering dirt and other impurities. Clean leaves were dried in a tray drier (Model 119, Creative Lab World, India) at 65°C until completely dried (Freitas et al., 2018), followed by grinding in a domestic grinder (Philips HL 7699/00) to make fine powder.

Pre-treatment of kinnow with natural fungicide (Neem solution)

Three different concentrations of fungicide, i.e., 3, 5, and 7%, were prepared by adding 30, 50, and 70 g of neem leaf powder in 1 L of water, respectively. The resulting solutions were filtered with a cotton cloth to obtain only an aqueous solution. Then, kinnow fruits were divided into three parts

and immersed separately in prepared neem leaf solutions for 1 min (Freitas et al., 2018). After treatment, the fruits were kept at room temperature for 5 h for surface drying (Richa et al., 2014).

Preparation of the scavenger sachet and storage

Iron powder, activated charcoal, and potassium permanganate were used as oxygen, carbon dioxide, and ethylene scavengers, respectively. Weighed quantities of these powders were packed separately in small pouches prepared from filter paper (inner layer) and high-density non-woven polypropylene (outer layer) has 0.11 mm thickness, 8-15 μm pore size, and 0.9 ± 0.2 g/ml density (Shalini, 2017; Kumar and Thakur, 2020). Pre-treated kinnow (1kg \pm 50g) was packed in LDPE pouches along with a scavenger sachet and stored in a cold chamber for 90 days at $6\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and 90-95% RH (Baswal et al., 2020). Observations were done at the interval of 5 days in terms of quality parameters viz. gas composition, physiological loss in weight, ascorbic acid, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, colour difference, firmness, microbial load, and shelf life.

Experimental design and optimization

The relationship between independent variables (dose of scavenger, fungicide concentration, and polythene thickness) and responses (O_2 and CO_2 gas concentration, physiological loss in weight, firmness, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, color difference, microbial load, and shelf life) was examined by using a three level and three factor Box–Behnken design (BBD). The corresponding levels of the three independent or process variables were selected based on previous literature and preliminary findings. These included: A, dose of scavenger (3-5 g), based on the effective range reported by Richa et al. (2014); B, fungicide concentration (5-7%), as recommended by Freitas et al. (2018) for effective microbial control while ensuring product safety; and C, polythene thickness (100-200 gauge), in accordance with the optimal packaging ranges suggested by Kumar and Thakur (2020) for maintaining moisture and gas barrier properties during storage. Table 1 shows the details of all 17 combinations of independent variables. All the experiments were done in triplicate. The relative effects of independent variables on the responses were evaluated by developing the second-order polynomial mathematical models.

Quality parameters of kinnow

The headspace gas composition (%), i.e., O_2 and CO_2 , was recorded at equal intervals of time using a portable Headspace Gas Analyzer (Model GS 3/P, Systech Instruments, Thames, UK). Headspace gas samples were taken by means of a hypodermic needle inserted through an adhesive septum (Mahajan et al., 2016). The firmness of fruits was measured using a handheld penetrometer (Tr di turonil Co. Snc. Italy) with 8 mm stainless steel probe, and results were expressed in terms of kg force (kgf) (Baswal et al., 2020). Yeast and mold counts were recorded using the method suggested by Farzana et al. (2017), and ascorbic acid (mg/100ml) using Indophenol dye was determined as described by Aggarwal et al. (2022).

Weight loss (%) and acidity (%) were determined according to the standard methods given in AOAC (2000). A hand-held refractometer ($0-32^\circ\text{B}$) was used to record total soluble solids. The color was recorded as L, a, and b values using Color Reader CR-10 colorimeter (Konica Minolta Sensing Inc.) & color difference (ΔE) was calculated using following formula, where L, a, and b represent the color values on the first day of storage, and L_s , a_s , and b_s correspond to the color values of the samples after storage.

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(L_s - L)^2 + (a_s - a)^2 + (b_s - b)^2}$$

Statistical analysis

The final data was analyzed statistically using Design Expert (version 13.0.1.0) to determine the effects of different independent variables on dependent parameters. Least significant difference was calculated at 5% level of significance.

Results and Discussion

The effect of different independent variables, i.e., dose of scavenger, fungicide concentration, and polythene thickness, was investigated on the quality parameters and shelf life of kinnow fruit. It was observed that O_2 and CO_2 gas concentration, physiological loss in weight, firmness, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, color difference, microbial load, and shelf life varied from 6.10 to 15.36%, 2.10 to 14.43%, 5.30 to 10.05%, 2.11 to 4.44 kgf, 9.20 to 13.10 $^\circ\text{B}$, 0.23 to 1.71%, 17.11 to 35.71 mg/100ml, 0.22 to 7.99, 5.10 to 9.80 $\times 10^3$ cfu/ml, and 15 to 65 days respectively (Table 1). The effect of independent parameters on the responses at linear, interaction, and quadratic levels has been studied (see Table 2); the significant ($p < 0.05$) regression coefficient values were

highlighted with an asterisk (*), where the quadratic response surface model was further used for the statistical analysis. The values of R^2 for all the responses were more than 0.85 and the lack-of-fit test was found to be highly insignificant, indicating the selected model was sufficiently accurate for the prediction of responses.

Table 1. Different combinations of independent variables along with responses obtained during active packaging of kinnow

Independent variables	Responses											
	Dose of scavenger (g)	Fungicide concentration (%)	Polythene thickness (gauge)	O ₂ gas concentration (%)	CO ₂ gas concentration (%)	Physiological loss in weight (%)	Firmness (kgf)	Total Soluble Solids (°B)	Titrateable acidity (%)	Ascorbic acid (mg/100ml)	Color difference	Microbial load (x10 ³ cfu/ml)
4	5	150	6.1	14.2	9.01	2.58	11.3	0.23	20.81	4.35	9.8	30
4	3	200	12.07	10.84	5.3	3.11	12.3	0.40	23.97	5.09	5.4	50
5	5	200	9.63	9.9	6.61	2.89	11	1.09	24.09	0.22	5.3	65
4	5	150	8.43	14.4	8.94	2.56	11.4	0.89	17.11	3.78	8.5	30
3	5	100	11.78	11.2	9.42	2.59	12	0.45	21.65	7.99	7.9	15
5	5	100	9.65	9.04	9.11	3.21	11.8	0.4	19.89	4.51	7.1	35
4	5	150	8.19	14.09	8.91	2.41	11.6	0.36	17.56	3.05	9.1	30
4	5	150	8.22	11.3	9.67	2.38	11.7	0.41	17.81	2.7	8.8	30
4	7	100	10.4	8.85	8.3	3.37	12.2	0.58	24.79	6.2	6.2	35
4	3	100	14.67	2.1	10.05	3.69	10.9	0.84	27.13	6.62	8.1	20
4	5	150	8.77	14.43	9.43	2.11	11.1	0.43	17.36	2.12	9.5	25
3	5	200	10.92	11.97	6.24	2.9	12	0.51	20.76	3.11	8.7	45
5	3	150	9.59	10.93	5.7	3.55	13.1	0.51	21.82	5.35	5.5	40
3	7	150	8.3	12.2	5.4	3.89	12.5	0.43	21.47	5.83	6.4	40
4	7	200	12.15	6.05	7.3	4.44	9.2	1.71	35.71	2.84	7.5	60
5	7	150	11.01	5.67	7.48	4.34	10.6	0.96	29.17	1.81	5.1	55
3	3	150	15.36	9.85	7.9	3.27	12.1	0.48	23.26	7.47	6.3	20

Fig. S1. Response surface 3-D plot showing the effect of independent variables on (A-B) O₂ gas concentration, (C-D) CO₂ gas concentration and (E-F) physiological loss in weight

Oxygen gas concentration

It can be observed from Table 2 that A and B were the significant ($p < 0.05$) parameters that affected the concentration of oxygen at the linear level; AB and BC at the interaction level, whereas B^2 and C^2 at the quadratic level. It was noted that the O₂ concentration decreased by increasing the dose of scavenger and fungicide concentration, as illustrated in Fig. S1 (A-B). These findings align well with recent research showing how effective active oxygen scavengers are in reducing headspace O₂ and preventing oxidative spoilage. For instance, iron-based sachets and scavengers embedded in packaging materials have been shown to bring O₂ levels down to nearly undetectable amounts (below 0.01%) when used with low oxygen-permeable films (Cichello, 2015). In another study, a gallic acid-based scavenger film cut dissolved O₂ levels by half within just 24 hours under refrigeration (Coray and Yildirim, 2024). It might be due to higher scavenging of O₂ by 5g scavenger than other scavengers and thus, preventing deterioration due to oxidation and growth of microorganism (Aday et al., 2011). Fungicide treatments, especially those using neem extract also played a key role in reducing O₂ levels. When used at higher concentrations, these treatments appear to support the action of O₂ scavengers by slowing down microbial respiration, helping to keep internal oxygen levels low. This combined effect is similar to what was observed in studies on

orange juice packaging, where oxygen-scavenging films helped block O₂ entry and preserved both vitamin C and flavor quality (Xu et al., 2012). In fact, higher doses of neem extract can suppress the growth of aerobic microbes and fungal pathogens, leading to less overall O₂ consumption inside the packaging (Strano et al., 2022).

Fig. S2. Response surface 3-D plot showing the effect of independent variables on (A) firmness, (B-C) total soluble solids, (D) titratable acidity, (E-F) ascorbic acid, and (G-H) microbial load

Carbon dioxide gas concentration

In the present study, AB and BC had a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on CO₂ concentration at the interaction level; B² and C² at the quadratic level, whereas only A was found significant at the linear level (Table 2). The CO₂ concentration decreased with an increase in the dose of scavenger, i.e., packaging with higher scavenger dose had lower CO₂ concentration as compared to that contained

lower dosages of scavenger (Fig. S1 C-D). This might be due to the scavenging activity of scavengers, which can reduce the increase in gas pressure inside the package by absorbing carbon dioxide produced through respiration (Aday et al., 2011).

Physiological loss in weight

Among all the variables under this research, C was the only parameter that significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected the loss in physiological weight at the linear level, A^2 and B^2 at the quadratic level, whereas AB and BC at the interaction level (Table 2). It was noticed from Fig S1 (E-F), that the physiological loss in weight decreased with an increase in the polythene thickness indicating thicker LDPE bags retained better physiological quality & moisture in fruits as compared to thinner LDPE. This can be correlated to higher relative humidity maintenance inside the thick package, thus, reducing transpiration losses and ultimately physiological loss in weight of packaged commodity (Kumar and Thakur, 2020). According to Kaur et al. (2013) thicker polythene helps to maintain the moisture of packed commodity by creating a saturated micro-atmosphere around it and preventing dehydration. Moreover, it slowed down the rate of transpiration by restricting the diffusion of gases thus, reduced physiological loss in weight. Similar results had been reported by Buthelezi and Mafeo (2024) where the authors found comparatively less weight loss of avocado in thick polythene (40 μm) than 20 μm thickness polythene.

Kumar and Thakur (2020) concluded that during cold storage of 60 days, 50.8 μm LDPE packaging effectively lessen the weight loss of pear fruit with 7.4% loss whereas 8% loss was reported in fruits that packed in bags with 25.4 μm thickness. However, 3D graph shows that at low fungicide and scavenger levels, microbial control is weak, but limited respiration may cause only moderate weight loss. At moderate levels, respiration and transpiration are more active due to partial microbial suppression and sufficient oxygen, leading to peak weight loss. At high levels, strong scavenger action limits oxygen, and high fungicide doses suppress microbial and enzymatic activity together reducing respiration, transpiration, and thereby minimizing physiological weight loss.

Firmness

Firmness of kinnow fruits was significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by A^2 and B^2 at quadratic level; BC at interaction level, whereas A and B at linear level as shown in Table 2. It is revealed from Fig S2 (A), that the higher firmness had been recorded for fruits packed with higher scavenger dose as well as fungicide concentration. Similar results for dose of scavenger have been reported by Niazmand and Yeganehzad (2020) for packed barberries using oxygen-scavenger sachets under refrigerated conditions. The authors concluded that packages with effective O_2 scavenging maintained higher fruit firmness, attributed to the suppression of microbial and enzymatic degradation pathways that typically soften tissues. Arowora et al. (2013) revealed that the retention of firmness in fruits treated with higher fungicide concentration may be due to decline in breakdown of insoluble protopectins into soluble pectin and pectic acid. It was revealed that during the ripening of fruits, shortening or depolymerization of chain length of pectin substances occurs with an increase in polygalacturonase and pectinesterase activities. Hence low O_2 and high CO_2 concentrations reduce the activities of these enzymes and allows retention of the firmness during storage. Similar results had been reported by Wijewardane and Guleria (2009) where researchers found that the treatment with 2% neem oil was the most effective for retaining firmness (i.e., 66.4-67.3 N) of apple fruit than 1% and 1.5% concentration.

Total soluble solids

All three parameters i.e., A, B, and C at linear level; A^2 and C^2 at quadratic level; whereas AB and BC at interaction level were the most significant ($p < 0.05$) parameters that affects the total soluble solids of kinnow fruit (Table 2). As shown in Fig S2 (B-C), total soluble solids decreased with an increase in the dose of scavenger, fungicide concentration, and polythene thickness. In our work, higher scavenger dose can delay in ripening process of fruit due to less availability of oxygen inside the package thus slower the conversion of starches into sugars. As a result, scavenger dose had negative effect on total soluble solids. Fruits treated with higher fungicide concentration had lower total soluble solids and vice versa. Similar results have been reported by Freitas et al. (2018). The authors reported that papaya fruits treated with 10% neem leaf extract substantially inhibited increase in total soluble solids during storage than lower levels. The reduction in metabolic process, rate of respiration, and slower conversion of starch to sugars might have delayed the ripening process (Liaquat et al., 2019). Fruits packed in thicker LDPE bags had lower total soluble solids as compared to those packed in thinner packaging. These findings were in agreement with the work carried out by Baswal (2019), who reported that the kinnow fruits packed in 150 gauge of polythene thickness had lower total soluble solids i.e., 9.93 °B than fruits packed in 100 gauge. Adhikaria et al.

(2020) correlated this with retardation of ripening process due to slower respiration rate and metabolic activities.

Table 2. ANOVA and regression coefficient of second-order polynomial model for variables

Source	p-values (Responses)	O ₂ gas concentration (%)	CO ₂ gas concentration (%)	Physiological loss in weight (%)	Firmness (kgf)	Total Soluble Solids (°B)	Titratable acidity (%)	Ascorbic acid (mg/100ml)	Color difference	Microbial load (×10 ³ cfu/ml)	Shelf life (days)
Model	7.94*	13.68*	9.19*	2.41*	11.42*	0.464*	18.13*	3.20*	9.14*	29.0*	
A-Dose scavenger	-0.81*	-1.21*	-0.7950	0.1675*	-0.2625*	0.1366	0.9788	-1.56*	-0.7875*	9.38*	
B-Fungicide concentration	-1.23*	-0.1187	-0.1738	0.3025*	-0.4875*	0.1801*	1.87*	-0.9813*	-0.0125	7.5*	
C-Polythene thickness	-0.2163	0.9463	-1.43*	-0.0250	-0.30*	0.1808*	1.38*	-1.76*	-0.3	14.38*	
AB	2.12*	-1.90*	1.07*	0.3175	-0.725*	0.1245	2.29*	-0.4750	-0.1250	-1.25	
AC	0.21	0.0225	-1.88	-0.22	-0.2	0.1552	1.27	0.1475	-0.65*	0.0	
BC	1.09*	-2.88*	0.9375*	0.4125*	-1.10*	0.3928*	3.52*	-0.4575	1.0*	-1.25	
A ²	0.6478	-0.2270	-1.23*	0.2997*	0.6025*	-0.0690	-0.2512	0.3425	-1.43*	4.25*	
B ²	2.48*	-3.79*	-1.34*	1.05*	0.0525	0.2005	6.05*	1.57*	-1.88*	5.50*	
C ²	1.91*	-2.93*	-2.49	0.5332	-0.3225*	0.2178	3.72*	0.4150	-0.4575	6.75*	
Lack of Fit	0.9655	0.4736	0.7904	0.7038	0.6486	0.8390	0.4723	0.3828	0.5830	0.4028	
R ²	0.9485	0.9308	0.9855	0.9739	0.9736	0.8586	0.9556	0.9145	0.9573	0.9882	
C.V. (%)	7.98	12.91	3.64	5.33	1.88	33.14	6.75	21.87	6.68	6.40	
Adj. R ²	0.8823	0.8418	0.7801	0.6294	0.9396	0.6769	0.8986	0.8046	0.9024	0.9731	
Predicted R ²	0.8758	0.4599	0.0311	0.3904	0.8404	0.4264	0.6530	0.2507	0.7142	0.8995	

* is significant (p<0.05)

Titratable acidity

The BC showed significant (p<0.05) results for the titratable acidity at the interaction level; B and C at the linear level; however, none of the independent variables were found to have a significant effect at the quadratic level (Table 2). Fig S2 (D) shows that the titratable acidity increased with an increase in the fungicide concentration and polythene thickness. Zewdie et al. (2022) studied tomatoes treated with nectar extract and edible coatings and found that those coated with a combination of 9% beeswax and 25% neem leaf extract maintained their titratable acidity (TA)

much better over a 36-day storage period compared to untreated fruits. This slower drop in acidity was likely due to reduced respiration and slower breakdown of organic acids, thanks to the improved gas barrier provided by the coating. It might have happened due to the decrease in metabolic activity of organic acids. Similarly, Ahlawat et al. (2018) reported that the coating delayed the respiration rate and conversion of organic acids into sugars. Fruits packed in thicker polythene had higher titratable acidity as compared to fruits packed in thinner LDPE. It might be due to decrease in respiration rate followed by delay in ripening might have prevented the acidity reduction (Khankeshi et al., 2018). These results are supported by Ediriweera et al. (2016), who found that avocados stored in thicker LDPE films (40 μm) held on to significantly more titratable acidity over 12 days compared to those packed in thinner films (20 μm). The better performance was credited to the thicker film's stronger barrier against oxygen, which helped slow down respiration and the breakdown of acids. Richa et al. (2014) revealed that maximum titratable acidity was retained in 125 gauge polythene thickness than 75 and 100 gauge.

Table 3. Selection criteria for the numerical optimization for active packaging of kinnow

Name	Goal	Lower limit	Upper limit
Dose of scavenger (g)	is in range	3	5
Fungicide concentration (%)	is in range	3	7
Polythene thickness (gauge)	is in range	100	200
O ₂ gas concentration (%)	minimize	6.1	15.36
CO ₂ gas concentration (%)	minimize	2.1	14.43
Physiological loss in weight (%)	minimize	5.3	10.05
Firmness (kgf)	maximize	2.11	4.44
Total Soluble Solids (°B)	minimize	9.2	13.1
Titratable acidity (%)	maximize	0.23	1.71
Ascorbic acid (mg/100ml)	maximize	17.11	35.71
Color difference	minimize	0.22	7.99
Microbial load ($\times 10^3$ cfu/ml)	minimize	5.1	9.8
Shelf life (days)	maximize	15	65

Table 4. The predicted optimized conditions for the active packaging of kinnow and their comparison with the experimental values of responses

Parameter	Predicted values	Actual values	Percentage deviation (%)
Dose of scavenger (g)	5	5	
Fungicide concentration (%)	6.83	7	
Polythene thickness (gauge)	192.12	200	
Desirability			0.812
O ₂ gas concentration (%)	12.84	12.45 \pm 0.60	3.04
CO ₂ gas concentration (%)	3.75	3.66 \pm 0.12	2.4
Physiological loss in weight (%)	7.34	7.19 \pm 0.27	2.04
Firmness (kgf)	4.44	4.3 \pm 0.02	3.15
Total Soluble Solids (°B)	9.2	9.4 \pm 0.43	2.17
Titratable acidity (%)	1.72	1.68 \pm 0.12	2.32
Ascorbic acid (mg/100ml)	35.28	34.09 \pm 1.51	3.37
Color difference	0.55	0.38 \pm 0.01	3.1
Microbial load ($\times 10^3$ cfu/ml)	4.87	5.0 \pm 0.03	2.67
Shelf life (days)	69	66 \pm 3.01	4.35

Ascorbic acid

Ascorbic acid of kinnow retained significantly ($p < 0.05$) with increasing B² and C² at quadratic level; AB and BC at interaction level; whereas B and C at linear level (Table 2). Fig S2 (E-F) shows that the fruits treated with higher neem leaf solution had higher ascorbic acid content. This can be related to impaired O₂ uptake by fruits due to coating with fungicide thereby slowing down their metabolism and consequently resulting in reduction in the rate of degradation/oxidation of ascorbic acid (Kumar, 2018). Similar results were reported by Palei et al. (2024), who studied mangoes treated with different concentrations of neem leaf extract (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%). They found that mangoes treated with 20% neem extract and kept in cold storage retained the highest levels of ascorbic acid (28.5 mg/100 g). These fruits also showed less weight loss and lower spoilage rates compared to those treated with lower concentrations. Likewise, Bhuvaneshwari et al. (2015) looked at onion slices treated with calcium lactate and packed in polypropylene films of different thicknesses (25 μm and 50 μm). The thicker 50 μm films helped reduce respiration, preserved more nutrients including vitamin C and kept the slices firmer after 12 days at 10 °C, compared to the thinner films. This might be due to low availability of O₂ for respiration owing to high barrier properties of the thicker film and degradation of ascorbic acid. In contrast, beyond an optimal point, very high fungicide levels or excessively thick packaging can restrict gas exchange, causing anaerobic conditions, moisture buildup, or stress-induced degradation. Therefore, moderate levels

of both treatments provide an optimal balance-sufficiently reducing oxygen exposure and microbial growth without disrupting the fruit's natural respiration or storage environment.

Color difference

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect of all independent variables, i.e., A, B, and C, on color difference of kinnow fruit at linear level; B^2 at quadratic level; whereas no significant effect of parameters at interaction level was observed in the present study (Table 2). Fruits packed with a higher dose of scavengers had lower color difference value as compared to those packed with a lower dosage. This negative effect can be due to lower oxygen and higher carbon dioxide concentration inside the package, which delays oxidation, respiration as well as enzyme reaction. Hence, color value was maintained by higher scavenger dosage (Custode, 2017). Fruits treated with higher fungicide concentration had lower color difference and vice versa. Similar results have been reported by Malik (2016) where kinnow fruits treated with a higher concentration of chemical fungicide (Azoxystrobin) showed lower color difference during storage. Munoz et al. (2008) concluded that the control of moisture loss by coatings might have contributed to minimize external color changes. Also, kinnow fruits packed in thicker LDPE bags had lower color difference. The results of the present study are in agreement with the findings of Zhai et al. (2020), who reported that packaging Cuixiang kiwifruit in thicker modified-atmosphere films helped maintain lower oxygen and higher carbon dioxide concentrations. This modified internal atmosphere significantly delayed respiration, oxidation, and enzymatic browning, ultimately reducing chilling injury and preserving fruit color during cold storage.

Microbial load

As evident from Table 2, only one parameter i.e., A at linear level had significant effect while AC and BC at interaction level whereas A^2 and B^2 were found significant ($p < 0.05$) at quadratic level. The microbial load decreased with an increase in the dose of scavenger (Fig S2 G-H). However, beyond an optimal point, further increase appears to reduce efficacy might be due to the saturation of active antimicrobial agents, development of microbial resistance, and chemical antagonism or instability at higher doses. Similar findings were reported by Lee et al. (2018), where the application of a sulfite-based oxygen scavenger in kimchi packaging significantly reduced headspace oxygen and microbial load, without affecting the natural fermentation process. The treated samples showed a significant reduction in total aerobic bacteria (up to 2.97 log CFU/g) and yeasts/molds (up to 3.04 log CFU/g) during 12 weeks of storage. The reduction in microbial load with increasing scavenger dose is primarily due to the decreased availability of oxygen in the packaging environment. Many spoilage microorganisms and aerobic bacteria require oxygen for growth and metabolic activity. By absorbing oxygen, scavengers create a low-oxygen or anaerobic environment, which inhibits the growth of these microbes (Cichello, 2015).

Shelf life

Shelf life of kinnow was affected significantly by all the process parameters at both linear and quadratic levels; whereas no parameter was found to be significant at interaction level (Table 2). It was seen that the shelf life was positively affected with the dose of scavenger, fungicide concentration, and polythene thickness. The use of all three independent parameters at higher level was effective in enhancing the quality and shelf life of kinnow fruit during cold storage. Hence, active packaging might be an effective way to maintain or delay in the changes in all the dependent parameters and could be considered as a suitable non-chemical treatment for the shelf-life extension and conservation of quality parameters without any chemical hazards for human consumption. Khan et al. (2021) concluded that 30% neem leaf extract could be considered a suitable coating for shelf-life enhancement of grapefruit than lower (10% and 20%) coating concentrations. The positive findings of polythene thickness and dose of scavenger were in line with the study carried out by Kumar and Thakur (2020) who observed that fruit could be safely stored at cold conditions up to 4 months when packed in LDPE bags (50.8 μm) in the presence of 15% oxygen scavenger i.e., iron powder.

Numerical Optimization

To find out the optimum conditions for storage of kinnow fruit, intensity and goals was allocated to each independent variable and responses. The main criteria for optimization of constraints were to minimize O_2 and CO_2 gas concentration, physiological loss in weight, total soluble solids, color difference, microbial load, and maximize firmness, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, shelf life while the process parameters should be within range (Table 3). The optimized conditions for active packaging of kinnow fruit were 5 g dose of scavenger, 6.83% fungicide concentration, and 192.12 gauge of polythene thickness with 0.812 overall desirability. Corresponding to these variables, the

predicted value of O₂ gas concentration, CO₂ gas concentration, physiological loss in weight, firmness, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, color difference, microbial load, and shelf life were 12.84%, 3.75%, 7.34%, 4.44 kgf, 9.2°B, 1.72%, 35.28 mg/100ml, 0.55, 4.87×10³ cfu/ml, and 69 days respectively (Table 4). For the model validation of optimized value, percentage deviation between the predicted and actual values were calculated for various parameters as shown in Table 4. Percent deviation was less than 5% for all the quality parameters.

Conclusion

The present study elucidates the significant effect of three independent variables i.e., dose of scavenger, fungicide concentration, and polythene thickness on the postharvest physiology, physicochemical quality, and shelf life of kinnow fruits under cold storage. Statistical analysis confirmed that these variables exhibited notable effects ($p < 0.05$) on key quality attributes, including gas concentration (O₂ and CO₂), physiological loss in weight, firmness, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, color difference, microbial load, and shelf life. Higher doses of scavenger and fungicide, in combination with increased polythene thickness, was associated with reduced oxidative degradation and respiration rates, thereby delaying senescence and microbial spoilage. The fitted second-order polynomial regression models demonstrated strong predictive capacity ($R^2 > 0.85$) and non-significant lack-of-fit, validating their applicability for process optimization. Overall, the results underscore the potential of active packaging strategies, incorporating tailored scavenger systems and bio-based fungicidal treatments within optimized polymeric films as an effective, non-chemical approach to extend the storage life and preserve the nutritional and sensory quality of citrus fruits. These findings hold substantial implications for sustainable postharvest management and value retention in commercial citrus supply chains.

Future Scope

Future studies should focus on evaluating the commercial scalability and economic feasibility of the proposed active packaging system. The use of biodegradable films in place of LDPE offers a promising direction for enhancing environmental sustainability. Further research on combining oxygen scavengers with other active agents (e.g., ethylene absorbers or natural antimicrobials) may yield synergistic effects on quality retention. Integrating smart indicators for real-time monitoring and exploring fruit physiological responses at the molecular level could deepen mechanistic understanding. Validation across different citrus varieties and under dynamic cold-chain conditions would also improve the applicability of this technology.

References

- Aday MS, Caner C and Rahvali F (2011) Effect of oxygen and carbon dioxide absorbers on strawberry quality. *Postharvest Biology and Technology* 62(2): 179-187.
- Adhikaria P, Dhakalb A, Pahadia K, et al. (2020) Effect of different plastic packaging on postharvest quality of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* mill.). *Tropical Agroecosystems* 1(1): 15-18.
- Adhikary T, Gill PPS, Jawandha SK, et al. (2022) Postharvest quality response of pear with beeswax coatings during long term cold storage. *The Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology* 97(6): 785-798.
- Aggarwal P, Kaur S and Kaur N (2022) Intermediate moisture kinnow bar from low grade kinnow mandarins: Phytonutritional profile, morphological characterization, and storage stability. *Food Bioscience* 49: 101837.
- Ahlawat P, Bala S and Kumar J (2018) Effect of post-harvest treatments of gum arabic, calcium lactate and glycerin on biochemical constituents of kinnow. *Crop Research* 53(3&4): 154-159.
- Ali MA, Zulfiqar A, Arif AM, et al. (2015). Effect of natural and synthetic fruit coating on the postharvest quality of kinnow mandarins. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal* 17(1): 197-206.
- AOAC (2000). *Methods of Analysis*, 16th Ed., Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, DC.
- Arowora KA, Williams JO, Adetunji CO, et al. (2013) Effects of Aloe Vera Coatings on Quality Characteristics of Oranges Stored Under Cold Storage. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 3(1): 39-47.
- Baswal AK (2019) Effect of postharvest treatments and packaging on storage life and quality of kinnow fruit. PhD Thesis, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India.

- Baswal AK, Dhaliwal HS, Singh Z, et al. (2020) Influence of types of modified atmospheric packaging (map) films on cold-storage life and fruit quality of 'kinnow' mandarin (*Citrus nobilis* Lour. \times *C. deliciosa* Tenora). *International Journal of Fruit Science* 20(S3): S1552-S1569.
- Bhan C, Asrey R, Meena NK, et al. (2022) Guar gum and chitosan-based composite edible coating extends the shelf life and preserves the bioactive compounds in stored Kinnow fruits. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 222 (Part B): 2922-2935.
- Bhuvanewari S, Narayana CK, Udhayakumar R, et al. (2015) Effect of packaging and storage temperature on shelf-life of minimally processed onion (*Allium cepa* L.). *Journal of Horticultural Sciences* 10(2): 216-219.
- Buthelezi NMD and Mafeo TP (2024) Effect of perforated low-density polyethylene films on postharvest quality of avocado fruit. *Heliyon* 10(5).
- Cichello SA (2015) Oxygen absorbers in food preservation: a review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 52: 1889-1895.
- Coray NM and Yildirim S (2024) Application of a Gallic Acid-Based Oxygen Scavenger Label for the Preservation of L-Ascorbic Acid in Orange Juice. *Packaging Technology and Science* 37(9): 917-923.
- Custode ISA, Campbell JA, Cassar JR, et al. (2017) Oxygen Scavengers affect Gas Mixture and Color Stability of Master Packed Ground Beef. *Meat and Muscle Biology* 1(1).
- De Kruijf N, Van Beest M, Rijk R, et al. (2002) Active and intelligent packaging: applications and regulatory aspects. *Food Additives & Contaminants* 19(1): 144-162.
- Dhall RK (2013) Advances in Edible Coatings for Fresh Fruits and Vegetables: A Review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* 53(5): 435-450.
- Ediriweera S, Pathirana S and Jayasinghe C (2016) Effect of low-density polyethylene film thickness on shelf-life and quality of avocado fruit during storage. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation* 40(6): e12485.
- Esturk O, Ayhan Z and Gokkurt T (2013) Production and application of active packaging film with ethylene absorber to increase the shelf life of Broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *Italica*). *Packaging Technology and Science* 27(3): 179-191.
- Farzana T, Mohajan S, Saha T, et al. (2017) Formulation and nutritional evaluation of a healthy vegetable soup powder supplemented with soy flour, mushroom, and moringa leaf. *Food Science & Nutrition* 5(4): 911-920.
- Freitas RVDS, Souza PAD, Ferreira Senhor R, et al. (2018) Post-Harvest storage of papaya fruits coated with extracts of leaves and fruits of neem. *Revista Caatinga* 31(2): 290-296.
- Gupta N and Jain SK (2014) Storage behavior of mango as affected by post-harvest application of plant extracts and storage conditions. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 51: 2499-2507.
- Jha A, Garg S, Satpute S, et al. (2024) Isotherm and kinetic modelling for assessing the effectiveness of economical adsorbents in sewage water treatment. *Indian Journal of Chemical Technology* 31(03): 438-450.
- Kaur K, Dhillon WS and Mahajan BVC (2013) Effect of different packaging materials and storage intervals on physical and biochemical characteristics of pear. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 50(1): 147-152.
- Khan A, Azam M, Shen J, et al. (2021) Overall quality maintenance of grapefruit during cold storage using pre-storage neem leaf extract dipping. *Journal of Food Measurement and Characterization* 15(11): 1727-1736.
- Khankeshi L, Tabatabaekolour R and Hashemi SJ (2018) Effects of Polyethylene Thickness, Gas Combination and Temperature on Shelf Life and Quality of Strawberry. *Journal of Research and Innovation in Food Science and Technology* 7(4): 377-392.
- Kumar S (2018) Standardization of post-harvest treatments and active packaging conditions for retaining storage quality of pear (*Pyrus Communis* L.). PhD Thesis, Dr. Yashwant Singh Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry, Solan, India.
- Kumar S and Thakur KS (2020) Active packaging technology to retain storage quality of pear cv. "Bartlett" during shelf-life periods under ambient holding after periodic cold storage. *Packaging Technology and Science* 33(7): 239-254.

- Lee JS, Jeong S, Lee HG, et al. (2018) Development of a sulfite-based oxygen scavenger and its application in kimchi packaging to prevent oxygen-mediated deterioration of kimchi quality. *Journal of Food Science* 83(12): 3009-3018.
- Liaquat M, Ahmad S, Khan A S, et al. (2019) Reduction in fruit rot and enhancement in fruit quality of kinnow mandarin by calcium chloride application. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 56(2): 367-376.
- Mahajan BVC, Singh R and Kumar M (2016) Quality assurance and shelf-life extension of kinnow mandarin fruit under supermarket conditions. *International Journal of Fruit Science* 16(1): 94-102.
- Mahajan BVC, Tandon R, Kapoor S, et al. (2018) Natural coatings for shelf-life enhancement and quality maintenance of fresh fruits and vegetables-A review. *Journal of Postharvest Technology* 6(1): 12-26.
- Malik AA, Ahmed N, Babita, et al. (2016) Plant extracts in post-harvest disease management of fruits and vegetables-A Review. *Journal of Food Processing & Technology* 7(6): 1-5.
- Malik S (2016) Comparative studies on pretreatments for shelf-life enhancement of kinnow under different storage condition. M.Tech. Thesis, G.B. Pant University of Agricultural and Technology, Pantnagar, India.
- Munoz PH, Almenar E, Valle VD, et al. (2008) Effect of chitosan coating combined with postharvest calcium treatment on strawberry (*Fragaria X ananassa*) quality during refrigerated storage. *Food Chemistry* 110(2): 428-435.
- Niazmand R and Yeganehzad S (2020) Capability of oxygen-scavenger sachets and modified atmosphere packaging to extend fresh barberry shelf life. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture* 7: 1-14.
- Palei S, Badu M, Kabi M, et al. (2024) Efficacy of plant extracts to prolong shelf life: A study on neem and turmeric in preservation of mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) fruits. *Journal of Advances in Biology & Biotechnology* 27(11): 1129-1139.
- Ramos B, Miller FA, Brandão TRS, et al. (2013) Fresh fruits and vegetables-An overview on applied methodologies to improve its quality and safety. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies* 20: 1-15.
- Randhawa JS, Jawandha SK and Gill PPS (2009) Effect of high density polyethylene packaging with edible oil and wax coating on storage quality of 'Kinnow' mandarin. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 46(2): 169-171.
- Richa R, Pandey JP, Khan C, et al. (2014) Optimization of storage parameters to enhance the shelf life of malta using response surface Method. *Indian Journal of Engineering* 8(18): 11-19.
- Shalini (2017) Studies on storage of kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa* Chev.) by using active packaging. M.Sc. Thesis, Dr. Yashwant Singh Parmar University of Horticulture and Forestry, Solan, Himachal Pradesh, India.
- Strano MC, Altieri G, Allegra M, et al. (2022) Postharvest technologies of fresh citrus fruit: Advances and recent developments for the loss reduction during handling and storage. *Horticulturae* 8(7): 612.
- Wijewardane RMNA and Guleria SPS (2009) Combined Effects of Pre-cooling, Application of Natural Extracts and Packaging on the Storage Quality of Apple (*Malus domestica*) cv. Royal Delicious. *Tropical Agricultural Research* 21(1): 10-20.
- Xu WC, Li DL, Fu YB, et al. (2012) Effect of oxygen scavenging packaging on orange juice quality. *Advanced Materials Research* 380: 248-253.
- Yadav R and Ray A (2010) Incorporation of oxygen scavenger sachet for active packaging of minimally processed orange (*Citrus sinensis*). *Haryana Journal of Horticultural Sciences* 39(3-4): 228-231.
- Zewdie B, Shonte TT and Woldetsadik K (2022) Shelf life and quality of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) fruits as affected by neem leaf extract dipping and beeswax coating. *International Journal of Food Properties* 25(1): 570-592.
- Zhai R, Li X, Wang Y, et al. (2020) Effect of different packaging film thicknesses on chilling injury in postharvest 'Cuixiang' kiwifruit. *Journal of Zhejiang University-Science B* 21(6): 469-480.

Author Contributions

PKP, VK, NK, GKS, AJ and SB conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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